

Med-CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: CORE Atmosphere variables

ag - agregation for subdaily output: i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

Version: 1 dec 2022

output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
tas	K	i	Near-Surface Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x				CORE	maximum from all integrated time steps per day minimum from all integrated time steps per day
tasmax	K		Daily Maximum Near-Surface Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x				CORE	
tasmin	K		Daily Minimum Near-Surface Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x				CORE	
pr	kg m-2 s-1	a	Precipitation	precipitation_flux	x	x				CORE	
prc	kg m-2 s-1	a	Convective Precipitation	convective_precipitation_flux	x	x				CORE	
evspsbl	kg m-2 s-1	a	Evaporation Including Sublimation and Transpiration	water_evapotranspiration_flux	x	x				CORE	
huss	1	i	Near-Surface Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x				CORE	
hurs	%	i	Near-Surface Relative Humidity	relative_humidity	x	x				CORE	
ps	Pa	i	Surface Air Pressure	surface_air_pressure	x	x				CORE	
psl	Pa	i	Sea Level Pressure	air_pressure_at_mean_sea_level	x	x				CORE	
sfcWind	m s-1	i	Near-Surface Wind Speed	wind_speed	x	x				CORE	
uas	m s-1	i	Eastward Near-Surface Wind	eastward_wind	x	x				CORE	
vas	m s-1	i	Northward Near-Surface Wind	northward_wind	x	x				CORE	
clt	%	a	Total Cloud Cover Percentage	cloud_area_fraction	x	x				CORE	
rsds	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	x	x				CORE	
rls	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	x	x				CORE	
mrros	kg m-2 s-1	a	Surface Runoff	surface_runoff_flux	x	x				CORE	
mrro	kg m-2 s-1	a	Total Runoff	runoff_flux	x	x				CORE	
hfls	W m-2	a	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux	x	x				CORE	
hfss	W m-2	a	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux	x	x				CORE	
zg500	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x				CORE	
ua500	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x				CORE	
va500	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x				CORE	
ta500	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x				CORE	
hus500	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x				CORE	
rsus	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	x	x				CORE	
rlus	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Longwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	x	x				CORE	
prw	kg m-2	i	Water Vapor Path	atmosphere_mass_content_of_water_vapor	x	x				CORE	
od550aer	1		atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol_particle	x	x				CORE	Total AOD including all the available species in the model
orog	m		Surface Altitude	surface_altitude			fx			CORE	
sftif	%		Percentage of the Grid Cell Occupied by Land	land_area_fraction			fx			CORE	

Med-CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 1 Atmosphere variables

ag - aggregation for subdaily output: i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

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output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments	
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr			
ts	K	i	Surface Temperature	surface_temperature	x	x				x	TIER 1	
tsl	K	i	Temperature of Soil	soil_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	Temperature of each soil layer (3D variable). Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
prhmax	kg m-2 s-1	i	Daily Maximum Hourly Precipitation Rate	precipitation_flux	x	x					TIER 1	Defined as maximum of the precipitation rate averaged over the whole hour.
prsn	kg m-2 s-1	a	Snowfall Flux	snowfall_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
snm	kg m-2 s-1	a	Surface Snow Melt	surface_snow_melt_flux	x	x	x				TIER 1	
tauv	Pa	a	Surface Downward Eastward Wind Stress	surface_downward_eastward_stress	x	x				x	TIER 1	
tauv	Pa	a	Surface Downward Northward Wind Stress	surface_downward_northward_stress	x	x				x	TIER 1	
sfcWindmax	m s-1	i	Daily Maximum Near-Surface Wind Speed	wind_speed	x	x					TIER 1	
sund	s	i	Daily Duration of Sunshine	duration_of_sunshine	x	x					TIER 1	Maximum from all integrated time steps per day
rsdsdir	W m-2	a	Surface Direct Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	surface_direct_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	x	x				x	TIER 1	The WMO definition of sunshine is that the surface incident radiative flux from the solar beam (i.e. excluding diffuse skylight) exceeds 120 W m-2.
rlut	W m-2	a	TOA Outgoing Longwave Radiation	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
rsdt	W m-2	a	TOA Incident Shortwave Radiation	toa_incoming_shortwave_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
rsut	W m-2	a	TOA Outgoing Shortwave Radiation	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
mrfso	kg m-2	i	Soil Frozen Water Content	soil_frozen_water_content	x	x	x				TIER 1	
mrfso	kg m-2	i	Frozen Water Content in Upper Portion of Soil Column	frozen_water_content_of_soil_layer	x	x				x	TIER 1	The mass of frozen water per unit area, summed over all soil layers. Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
mrfso	kg m-2	i	Frozen Water Content of Soil Layer	frozen_water_content_of_soil_layer	x	x	x				TIER 1	The mass of frozen water in the upper 10cm of the soil layer. Reported as missing for grid cells with no land. (not in CMIP)
mrfso	kg m-2	i	Total Soil Moisture Content	mass_content_of_water_in_soil	x	x	x				TIER 1	The mass of water in each soil layer (3D variable). Reported as missing for grid cells with no land. (not in CMIP)
mrfso	kg m-2	i	Moisture in Upper Portion of Soil Column	mass_content_of_water_in_soil_layer	x	x				x	TIER 1	The mass of water in all phases per unit area, summed over all soil layers.
mrfso	kg m-2	i	Total Water Content of Soil Layer	mass_content_of_water_in_soil_layer	x	x	x				TIER 1	The mass of water in all phases in the upper 10cm of the soil layer. Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
snw	kg m-2	i	Surface Snow Amount	surface_snow_amount	x	x					TIER 1	The mass of water in all phases in each soil layer (3D variable). Reported as missing for grid cells with no land.
snc	%	i	Snow Area Percentage	surface_snow_area_fraction	x	x	x				TIER 1	In water equivalent as reported in Terzago et al., 2017 that uses euro-cordex
snd	m	i	Snow Depth	surface_snow_thickness	x	x	x				TIER 1	
siconca	%	i	Sea-Ice Area Percentage (Atmospheric Grid)	sea_ice_area_fraction	x	x					TIER 1	daily and monthly means
zmla	m	i	Height of Boundary Layer	atmosphere_boundary_layer_thickness	x	x				x	TIER 1	
clwvi	kg m-2	i	Condensed Water Path	atmosphere_mass_content_of_cloud_condensed_water	x	x				x	TIER 1	
clivi	kg m-2	i	Ice Water Path	atmosphere_mass_content_of_cloud_ice	x	x				x	TIER 1	
ua1000	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua925	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua850	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua700	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua600	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua400	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua300	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua250	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua200	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va1000	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va925	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va850	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va700	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va600	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va400	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va300	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va250	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
va200	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta1000	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta925	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta850	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta700	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta600	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta400	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta300	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta250	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ta200	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus1000	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus925	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus850	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus700	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus600	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus400	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus300	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus250	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
hus200	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg1000	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg925	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg850	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg700	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg600	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg400	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg300	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg250	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
zg200	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa1000	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa925	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa850	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa700	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa600	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa500	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa400	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa300	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	

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ag - agregation for subdaily output; i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

Version: 1 dec 2022

output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments	
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr			
wa250	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
wa200	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x				TIER 1	
ua50m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 50m	eastward_wind	x	x				x	TIER 1	
ua100m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 100m	eastward_wind	x	x				x	TIER 1	
ua150m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 150m	eastward_wind	x	x				x	TIER 1	
va50m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 50m	northward_wind	x	x				x	TIER 1	
va100m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 100m	northward_wind	x	x				x	TIER 1	
va150m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 150m	northward_wind	x	x				x	TIER 1	
ta50m	K	i	Air Temperature at 50m	air_temperature	x	x				x	TIER 1	requested for urban modeling
hus50m	1	i	Specific Humidity at 50m	specific_humidity	x	x				x	TIER 1	requested for urban modeling
viwvn	kg m-1 s-1	i	Vertical integral of northward water vapour flux	vertical_integral_of_northward_water_vapour_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
viwve	kg m-1 s-1	i	Vertical integral of eastward water vapour flux	vertical_integral_of_eastward_water_vapour_flux	x	x				x	TIER 1	
tas	K	i	Near-Surface Air Temperature	air_temperature						x	TIER 1	
pr	kg m-2 s-1	a	Precipitation	precipitation_flux						x	TIER 1	
prc	kg m-2 s-1	a	Convective Precipitation	convective_precipitation_flux						x	TIER 1	
evpsbl	kg m-2 s-1	a	Evaporation Including Sublimation and Transpiration	water_evapotranspiration_flux						x	TIER 1	
huss	1	i	Near-Surface Specific Humidity	specific_humidity						x	TIER 1	
hurs	%	i	Near-Surface Relative Humidity	relative_humidity						x	TIER 1	
ps	Pa	i	Surface Air Pressure	surface_air_pressure						x	TIER 1	
psl	Pa	i	Sea Level Pressure	air_pressure_at_mean_sea_level						x	TIER 1	
sfcWind	m s-1	i	Near-Surface Wind Speed	wind_speed						x	TIER 1	
uas	m s-1	i	Eastward Near-Surface Wind	eastward_wind						x	TIER 1	
vas	m s-1	i	Northward Near-Surface Wind	northward_wind						x	TIER 1	
clt	%	a	Total Cloud Cover Percentage	cloud_area_fraction						x	TIER 1	
rsds	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Shortwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air						x	TIER 1	
rlds	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Longwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air						x	TIER 1	
mros	kg m-2 s-1	a	Surface Runoff	surface_runoff_flux						x	TIER 1	
mro	kg m-2 s-1	a	Total Runoff	runoff_flux						x	TIER 1	
hfis	W m-2	a	Surface Upward Latent Heat Flux	surface_upward_latent_heat_flux						x	TIER 1	
hfss	W m-2	a	Surface Upward Sensible Heat Flux	surface_upward_sensible_heat_flux						x	TIER 1	
zg500	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height						x	TIER 1	
ua500	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind						x	TIER 1	
va500	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind						x	TIER 1	
ta500	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature						x	TIER 1	
hus500	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity						x	TIER 1	
rsus	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Shortwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air						x	TIER 1	
rlus	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Longwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air						x	TIER 1	
prw	kg m-2	i	Water Vapor Path	atmosphere_mass_content_of_water_vapor						x	TIER 1	
od550aer	1	i	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol_pa	atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol_partic						x	TIER 1	

Med-CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 2 Atmosphere variables

ag - aggregation for subdaily output: i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

Version: 1 dec 2022

output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
tds	K	i	dew point temperature	dew_point_temperature	x	x			x	TIER 2	
tdw	K	i	wet bulb point temperature	wet_bulb_point_temperature	x	x			x	TIER 2	
evpsblpot	kg m-2 s-1	a	Potential Evapotranspiration	water_potential_evaporation_flux	x	x			x	TIER 2	
wsgsmax	m s-1	i	Daily Maximum Near-Surface Wind Speed of Gust	wind_speed_of_gust	x	x				TIER 2	
clh	%	a	High Level Cloud Fraction	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	x	x	x			TIER 2	above 440 hPa between 680 and 440 hPa below 680 hPa
clm	%	a	Mid Level Cloud Fraction	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	x	x	x			TIER 2	
cll	%	a	Low Level Cloud Fraction	cloud_area_fraction_in_atmosphere_layer	x	x	x			TIER 2	
rsdscs	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ridscs	W m-2	a	Surface Downwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	
rsuscs	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	
riuscs	W m-2	a	Surface Upwelling Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	surface_upwelling_longwave_flux_in_air_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	
rsutcs	W m-2	a	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Shortwave Radiation	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	
riutcs	W m-2	a	TOA Outgoing Clear-Sky Longwave Radiation	toa_outgoing_longwave_flux_assuming_clear_sky	x	x	x			TIER 2	
z0	m	i	Surface Roughness Length	surface_roughness_length	x	x				TIER 2	
CAPE	J kg-1	i	Convective Available Potential Energy	atmosphere_convective_available_potential_energy_wrt_surface	x	x		x		TIER 2	
LI	K	i	Lifted Index	temperature_difference_between_ambient_air_and_air_lifted_adiabatically_from_the_surface	x	x		x		TIER 2	
CIN	J kg-1	i	Convective Inhibition	atmosphere_convective_inhibition_wrt_surface	x	x		x		TIER 2	
CAPEmax	J kg-1	i	Daily Maximum Convective Available Potential Energy	atmosphere_convective_available_potential_energy_wrt_surface	x	x				TIER 2	
LImax	K	i	Daily Maximum Lifted Index	temperature_difference_between_ambient_air_and_air_lifted_adiabatically_from_the_surface	x	x				TIER 2	
CINmax	J kg-1	i	Daily Maximum Convective Inhibition	atmosphere_convective_inhibition_wrt_surface	x	x				TIER 2	
ua150	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ua100	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ua70	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ua50	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ua30	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ua20	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ua10	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
va150	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
va100	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
va70	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
va50	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
va30	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
va20	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
va10	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ta150	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ta100	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ta70	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ta50	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ta30	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ta20	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ta10	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x			TIER 2	
hus150	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
hus100	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
hus70	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
hus50	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
hus30	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
hus20	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
hus10	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
zg150	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 2	
zg100	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 2	
zg70	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 2	
zg50	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 2	
zg30	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 2	
zg20	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 2	
zg10	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 2	
wa150	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
wa100	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
wa70	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
wa50	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
wa30	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
wa20	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
wa10	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ua750	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind	eastward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	requested by CORDEX-Africa requested by CORDEX-Africa requested by CORDEX-Africa requested by CORDEX-Africa requested by CORDEX-Africa
va750	m s-1	i	Northward Wind	northward_wind	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ta750	K	i	Air Temperature	air_temperature	x	x	x			TIER 2	
hus750	1	i	Specific Humidity	specific_humidity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
zg750	m	i	Geopotential Height	geopotential_height	x	x	x			TIER 2	
wa750	m s-1	i	Upward Air Velocity	upward_air_velocity	x	x	x			TIER 2	
ua200m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 200m	eastward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 2	
ua250m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 250m	eastward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 2	
ua300m	m s-1	i	Eastward Wind at 250m	eastward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 2	

Med-CORDEX-CMIP6 Data Request: Tier 2 Atmosphere variables

ag - aggregation for subdaily output; i: instantaneous; a: averaged over output interval;

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output variable name	units	ag	long_name	standard_name	Output frequency					Priority	Comments
					mon	day	6hr	3hr	1hr		
va200m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 200m	northward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	Fita et al, GMD, doi: 10.5194/gmd-12-1029-2019 for a methodology
va250m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 250m	northward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	Fita et al, GMD, doi: 10.5194/gmd-12-1029-2019 for a methodology
va300m	m s-1	i	Northward Wind at 350m	northward_wind	x	x			x	TIER 1	Fita et al, GMD, doi: 10.5194/gmd-12-1029-2019 for a methodology
sftgif	%		Percentage of the Grid Cell Covered by Glacier	land_ice_area_fraction					fx	TIER 2	not in CMIP or in CF not in CMIP or in CF not in CMIP or in CF (lower boundary of land surface models)
mrsofc	kg m-2		Capacity of Soil to Store Water (Field Capacity)	soil_moisture_content_at_field_capacity					fx	TIER 2	
rootd	m		Maximum Root Depth	root_depth					fx	TIER 2	
sftlaf	%		Percentage of the Grid Cell Occupied by Lake	lake_area_fraction					fx	TIER 2	
sfturf	%		Percentage of the Grid Cell Occupied by City	urban_area_fraction					fx	TIER 2	
dtb	m		Depth to Bedrock	bedrock_depth					fx	TIER 2	
areacella	m2		Atmosphere Grid-Cell Area	cell_area					fx	TIER 2	
qc	kg kg-1	i	cloud mixing ratio	cloud_mixing_ratio					x	TIER2	suspend liquid water at the air
qr	kg kg-1	i	rain mixing ratio	rain_mixing_ratio					x	TIER2	suspend rain dropled in the air
qs	kg kg-1	i	snow mixing ratio	snow_mixing_ratio					x	TIER2	snow suspend in the air
qi	kg kg-1	i	ice mixing ratio	ice_mixing_ratio					x	TIER2	frozen water suspend in the air
qq	kg kg-1	i	graupel mixing ratio	graupel_mixing_ratio					x	TIER2	graupel suspend in the air
qh	kg kg-1	i	hail mixing ratio	hail_mixing_ratio					x	TIER2	hail suspend in the air